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ТЕРАПИЯ

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ИММУНОВОСПАЛИТЕЛЬНЫЕ МАРКЕРЫ РЕМОДЕЛИРОВАНИЯ ЛЕВОГО ЖЕЛУДОЧКА СЕРДЦА ПРИ ИШЕМИЧЕСКОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ СЕРДЦА

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Бухара

Аннотация. В статье автором изучены факторы эндотелиального повреждения при гипертонической болезни и ишемической болезни сердца, составляющих кардиоваскулярную синтропию. Цитокинами, являющимися маркерами эндотелиальной дисфункции, представлены IGF-I, VEGF, TGF- β 1 и прокальцитонин сыворотки крови. В исследовании установлено, что у пациентов с повышенным уровнем VEGF существует высокий риск развития и прогрессирования кардиоваскулярной патологии, в частности — фибросклерозирования и гипертрофии миокарда на фоне артериальной гипертензии независимо от степени её тяжести.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, ишемическая болезнь сердца, артериальная гипертензия, цитокины, иммунологические маркеры.

YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIGIDA SHAP QORINCHA QAYTA TUZILISHINING IMMYUN-YALLIG‘LANISH MARKERLARI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada yurak-qon tomir sinotropiyasini tashkil etuvchi gipertonik kasallik va yurak ishemik kasalligida endotelial shikastlanish omillari o‘rganilgan. Endotelial disfunktsiya markerlari sifatida IGF-I, VEGF, TGF- β 1 va qon zardobidagi prokaltsitonin ko‘rib chiqilgan. Tadqiqotda VEGF darajasi yuqori bo‘lgan

bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, xususan, miyokardning fibrosklerozi va gipertrofiyasi rivojlanish xavfi yuqori ekani aniqlangan — bu arterial gipertenziya darajasidan qat'i nazar kuzatilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, yurak ishemik kasalligi, arterial gipertenziya, sitokinlar, immunologik markerlar.

IMMUNO-INFLAMMATORY MARKERS OF LEFT VENTRICULAR REMODELING IN ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE

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Abstract. The article explores endothelial damage factors in arterial hypertension and ischemic heart disease, forming a cardiovascular syndrome. The cytokines considered as markers of endothelial dysfunction include IGF-I, VEGF, TGF- β 1, and serum procalcitonin. The study found that patients with elevated VEGF levels have a high risk of developing and progressing cardiovascular pathology—particularly myocardial fibrosis and hypertrophy—against the background of arterial hypertension, regardless of its severity.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, ischemic heart disease, arterial hypertension, cytokines, immunological markers.

Introduction. The immune system acts through the release of cytokines—small molecules involved in cellular signal transmission. Cytokines are the primary regulatory mediators of immunity and serve as ideal communicators between the nervous and immune systems, given that cytokines, like certain neuropeptides, can cross the blood-brain barrier. Several studies have described the role of neuropeptides and substance P, as well as various cytokines, in the modulation of cardiovascular diseases (CVD). This supports the possible involvement of these molecules in the onset and

maintenance of hypertensive states. The widespread expression of cytokines and substance P in peripheral organs and blood, along with their ability to cross the blood-brain barrier, convincingly suggests that these molecules act as messengers between the central nervous system (CNS), immune cells, and the cardiovascular system, thereby contributing to blood pressure homeostasis [2].

Currently, it is established that the pathogenesis of most cardiovascular and metabolic diseases—such as dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension (AH), ischemic heart disease (IHD), angina pectoris, diabetes mellitus, and obesity—is associated with systemic inflammation and oxidative stress. It is assumed that these pathological processes share common pathogenic pathways in these diseases [1, 3].

Objective: To determine informative immunological indicators of ischemic heart disease and hypertensive disease.

Materials and Methods: The study included 234 middle-aged patients with a mean age of 52.4 ± 1.27 years. Arterial hypertension (AH) was diagnosed following the World Health Organization (WHO) criteria and classified according to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10). The study adhered to the ACC/AHA Hypertension Guidelines (2017). Inclusion criteria comprised patients aged 45 to 59 years diagnosed with hypertensive disease (HD), ischemic heart disease (IHD), and stable exertional angina (SEA) confirmed by clinical and laboratory-instrumental methods, hospitalized for inpatient care. Patients in the study groups were comparable by age, sex, and presence of cardiovascular risk factors. Exclusion criteria included patients with acute myocardial infarction, acute coronary syndrome, acute infectious diseases, myocarditis and cardiomyopathies, chronic renal and hepatic failure, pulmonary hypertension, congenital and acquired heart defects, systemic diseases, oncological and hematological conditions. The research was conducted in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration.

Patient Grouping:

- Group 1 included 64 patients with hypertensive disease, stage 1, grade 1, risk II;

- Group 2 included 52 patients with ischemic heart disease: stable exertional angina, functional class II, hypertensive disease stage 2, grade 2, risk III;
- Group 3 included 58 patients with ischemic heart disease: stable exertional angina, functional class III, hypertensive disease stage 3, grade 3, risk IV;
- The control group consisted of 60 practically healthy individuals without cardiovascular pathology.

All patients underwent necessary functional tests (ECG, echocardiography, coronary angiography, abdominal ultrasound, chest X-ray). Laboratory analyses included protein, lipid, and carbohydrate blood profiles, coagulation tests, and measurement of cytokines and growth factors in serum.

Statistical analysis was performed using Microsoft Excel from the Microsoft Office XP suite (Microsoft, USA).

Results and Discussion: Immunological blood indicators in cardiovascular syntropy showed a tendency for proportional increases in cytokine concentrations correlating with disease severity: patients in Group 1 exhibited a 1.3-fold increase in IL-17A compared to the control group and a 1.25-fold increase in IL-1 β , while levels of other cytokines were similar to controls. In Group 2, IL-17A levels (99.9 ± 2.71 pg/mL) were doubled relative to controls (49.9 ± 2.65 pg/mL), and complement C3 increased by 1.4 times. In Group 3, IL-17A doubled, and IL-6 and C3 increased by 1.5 times. This proportional increase in cytokine levels with disease progression demonstrates the pathogenetic significance of immunological changes in cardiovascular pathology (see Table 1).

Cytokine Status in Cardiovascular Syntropy

Cytokines	Group 1 (n=64)	Group 2 (n=52)	Group 3 (n=58)	Control Group (n=60)
IL-1 β , pg/mL	$54.1 \pm 1.97^{**}$	$58.2 \pm 2.07^{**}$	$67.5 \pm 0.89^{***}$	43.2 ± 1.57
IL-6, pg/mL	$31.0 \pm 13.8^*$	$35.8 \pm 0.84^{***}$	$45.2 \pm 0.86^{***}$	29.8 ± 0.59

IL-17A, pg/mL	62.8 ± 1.61**	99.9 ± 2.71***	105.5 ± 1.08***	49.9 ± 2.65
TNF- α , pg/mL	32.1 ± 1.89*	50.2 ± 1.0**	50.4 ± 1.74**	30.2 ± 1.17
C3, ng/mL	53.2 ± 5.4*	68.2 ± 2.07***	73.0 ± 1.15***	50.2 ± 1.34

*Note: Values are statistically significant compared to control (*P<0.05; **P<0.01; ***P<0.001).*

In the study of growth factors IGF-1, VEGF-A, and TGF- β 1, an increased level of IGF-1 was observed in patients of Group 3, reaching 134.0 ± 0.05, compared to 127.7 ± 2.59 and 124.8 ± 2.18 in Groups 1 and 2, respectively (Table 2).

The elevated concentration of IGF-1 in ischemic heart disease can be considered as a mechanism activating both vascular wall injury and protection processes, as well as an indicator of “atherosclerotic plaque instability,” thereby indicating a higher risk of myocardial infarction.

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Table 2.

Immunological Growth and Injury Factors in the Progression of Arterial Hypertension to Ischemic Heart Disease

Blood Parameters	Group 1 (n=64)	Group 2 (n=52)	Group 3 (n=58)	Control Group
IGF-1	127.7 ± 2.59	124.8 ± 2.18	134.0 ± 0.05*	120.9 ± 1.44
VEGF-A	95.9 ± 7.1*	193.8 ± 0.05***	318.7 ± 16.52***	88.4 ± 1.61
TGF- β 1	21.9 ± 1.84	25.2 ± 0.05*	20.8 ± 0.90	22.7 ± 1.52

*Note: Values are statistically significant compared to the control group (*P<0.05;*

**** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$).**

Taking into account the pathogenetic mechanisms underlying the development of hypertensive disease (HD) and its progression to ischemic heart disease (IHD), the level of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) was measured in the selected patient groups. The results demonstrated an increased VEGF level in patients from Group 3, reaching 318.7 ± 16.52 pg/mL, compared to 95.9 ± 7.1 ng/mL and 193.8 ± 0.05 ng/mL in Groups 1 and 2, respectively ($p < 0.001-0.05$). In Group 3, the VEGF level was significantly elevated by 3.6 times, and in Group 2 by 2.4 times, indicating profound pathogenetically significant changes and severity of endothelial damage.

One of the key pathogenetic factors leading to the activation of myocardial fibrosis and hypertrophy is transforming growth factor-beta 1 (TGF- β 1). Experimental studies on cardiomyocyte cultures have demonstrated its role in the development of hypertrophy. Activation of TGF- β 1 is associated with the phenotypic heterogeneity of myofibroblasts and their ability to produce connective tissue, as these cells can synthesize glycoproteins, all types of collagen, and matrix-modifying proteins. This growth factor is linked to the development of interstitial fibrosis, as well as a reduction in the elastic properties of the myocardium and blood vessels.

Thus, the mechanism of arterial hypertension (AH) progression to ischemic heart disease is closely related to vascular endothelial dysfunction. The activity of growth factors and inflammatory markers holds important prognostic value for assessing cardiovascular disease progression and the development of other complications.

Correlation analysis revealed relationships between immunological parameters and coronary artery diameter: complement C3 ($r = -0.56$) and IL-17A ($r = -0.62$) showed strong negative correlations, while procalcitonin ($r = 0.28$), TNF- α ($r = 0.22$), and VEGF-A ($r = 0.35$) exhibited weak to moderate positive correlations with coronary vessel diameter (see Fig. 1).

The inverse relationships between complement C3 and IL-17A concentrations and coronary artery diameter indicate the diagnostic significance of these

cytokines in endothelial injury and suggest a high risk of atherothrombosis.

Figure 1. Correlation between coronary artery diameter in ischemic heart disease (IHD) and blood cytokine levels

During duplex angioscanning of the carotid arteries in 41 patients (23.6%), signs of atherosclerosis of the common carotid artery and a significant increase in intima-media thickness (IMT) were detected. This condition was observed in 12 patients (18.7%) in Group 1, 13 patients (24.6%) in Group 2, and 16 patients (27.6%) in Group 3. Correlation analysis revealed a moderate positive relationship between IMT and blood fibrinogen ($r = 0.38$) and creatinine ($r = 0.36$), as well as a statistically significant strong positive correlation with procalcitonin ($r = 0.52$) and IL-6 ($r = 0.64$) (see Fig. 2).

The significant correlations between procalcitonin concentration and the proinflammatory cytokine IL-6, both mediators of the systemic inflammatory response, indicate that vascular wall inflammation predominates in the processes of atherosclerosis and atherothrombosis.

Correlation analysis of immunological growth factors IGF-1, TGF- β 1, and VEGF-A with cytokines IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-17A, TNF- α , left ventricular ejection fraction, and left ventricular myocardial mass revealed the following relationships (see Fig. 3).

Figure 2. Correlation analysis of immunoinflammatory markers and intima-media thickness (IMT) of the common carotid artery

Figure 3. Correlation analysis of immunological growth factors, cytokines, and hemodynamic parameters

An increase in the concentrations of VEGF-A and IL-1 β , along with strong positive correlations with left ventricular end-systolic volume (LVESV), left ventricular end-diastolic volume (LVEDV), and left ventricular myocardial mass, as well as strong negative correlations with left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF) in ischemic heart disease (IHD), indicate a high risk of left ventricular dysfunction. Significant and prognostically relevant results were obtained for the correlation between VEGF-A and left ventricular myocardial mass ($r = 0.44$), and between VEGF-A and LVEF ($r = -0.52$).

IL-1 β also showed a strong positive correlation with left ventricular myocardial mass ($r = 0.44$) and a negative correlation with LVEF ($r = -0.46$). These indicators suggest a risk of developing left ventricular dysfunction.

Echocardiographic parameters of the left ventricle demonstrated notable negative correlations between left ventricular myocardial mass (LVMM) and IL-6 ($r = -0.31$), and a strong negative correlation between LVEF and IL-6 ($r = -0.41$). Meanwhile, LVESV showed a strong positive correlation with IL-1 β ($r = 0.40$), and LVEF was positively correlated with serum complement C3 concentration ($r = 0.41$) (see Fig. 4). Thus, LVEF decreases with increasing IL-6 levels, while LVESV increases with rising IL-1 β levels; both cytokines are pro-inflammatory and highlight the role of immune inflammation at the cardiac and vascular levels in IHD.

Further analysis revealed that systolic arterial pressure (SAP) directly correlates with fibrinogen concentration ($r = 0.30$) and inversely correlates with procalcitonin ($r = -0.30$) and IL-6 ($r = -0.26$). Additionally, a significant positive correlation was found between heart rate (HR) and serum creatinine ($r = 0.35$).

These established relationships demonstrate the contribution of the inflammatory (immune) syndrome to the progression of arterial hypertension (AH). Specifically, creatinine, fibrinogen, procalcitonin, and IL-6 serve as indicators of AH progression in IHD (see Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Correlation between echocardiographic parameters and cytokine levels in ischemic heart disease (IHD)

Thus, the correlations identified through analysis between blood parameters

and cardiac functional studies indicate the significant role of inflammatory syndrome in the progression of arterial hypertension (AH) to ischemic heart disease (IHD).

Figure 6. Correlation between immuno-biochemical parameters in ischemic heart disease (IHD)

The development of cardiac restructuring underscores the need to establish immunological and biochemical indicators for predicting the progression of arterial hypertension (AH) to ischemic heart disease (IHD) in middle-aged individuals.

It has been established that the dynamic assessment of immunological and biochemical blood markers, along with the application of these findings, allows for better control of arterial hypertension, enhances diagnostic accuracy, and supports appropriate treatment strategies in cases of cardiac remodeling.

Conclusions. It was determined that elevated levels of creatinine, fibrinogen, procalcitonin, and IL-6 in the blood serve as predictors for the development of ischemic heart disease in patients with arterial hypertension. These markers were found to be elevated in patients with carotid atherosclerosis as identified by duplex carotid ultrasound, in combination with pathological changes in the lipid profile.

The strong positive correlation identified between low-density lipoproteins (LDL), procalcitonin, IL-6, and carotid intima-media thickness (IMT) confirms that atherosclerotic vascular changes occur in the context of destructive inflammatory

processes, accompanied by the expression of proinflammatory cytokines and the systemic inflammatory response mediator—procalcitonin.

In patients with ischemic heart disease, a significant positive correlation was observed between VEGF-A and IL-1 β concentrations and increased left ventricular myocardial mass and dimensions, along with a strong negative correlation with left ventricular ejection fraction. These findings indicate a high risk of developing left ventricular dysfunction.

An increase in complement C3 and IL-17 levels was inversely correlated with coronary vessel diameter, suggesting a high risk of endothelial damage and coronary atherothrombosis.

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